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Technical Report:

Software management with Spack on the cluster Aries at UniMoRe for CNR-NANO

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Abstract

In 2023, the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia upgraded its computational infrastructure with Aries, a high-performance system to support research, teaching, and training. The Istituto Nanoscienze of CNR tasked me with designing a software installation methodology for the cluster. The methodology, centred on Spack, a powerful HPC package manager, was implemented successfully and made accessible to UniMoRe and CNR researchers.

Training sessions were conducted for system administrators, covering configuration details and Spack usage. This report summarises the setup process, its benefits for the research community, and provides a guide for replicating the approach on other clusters.

Keywords: Spack, package manager, software installation, UniMoRe, CNR-NANO, HPC, Aries.

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Introduction

In 2023, to strengthen the technological potential and quality of infrastructure and platform services for research, the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia¹ (UniMoRe) decided to invest in a new, more integrated system with enhanced performance and greater resilience, namely **Aries**. This upgrade aims to maximise the effectiveness of research, training, and teaching activities. Traditionally, great care was devoted to ensure a coherent evolution of the computing infrastructures of Unimore and CNR in Modena, including the shared use of computing resources. The Istituto Nanoscienze² of CNR therefore assigned to me the responsibility of organising an installation procedure for the software required by researchers of our centre. I designed a methodology, inspired by the system used at the CINECA³ supercomputing centre, to streamline this installation process, and presented it to the administrators of the new cluster.

The project was well-received, and I was asked to implement it to make it accessible to all researchers within the university. The core of this project involves the use of Spack⁴, a powerful package management tool designed for the flexible and efficient installation of scientific software.

Spack offers a comprehensive solution for managing software installations, particularly in high-performance computing (HPC) environments. It allows users to easily install and manage multiple versions of complex scientific applications with varying dependencies, greatly facilitating the software setup on clusters like the one in UniMoRe.

In this report it is first summarised the project's development, the setup process with Spack, and the expected benefits for the CNR and university's research community. This first part can be used as a baseline for the setup of new cluster installations, while the second part offers a synthetic user guide both for the installation and the use of the software.

The Aries Cluster

System description:

- 3 Master node: 24 core, 128 GB memoria
- Storage: BeeGFS 300TB

¹ <https://www.unimore.it/>

² <https://www.nano.cnr.it/>

³ <https://www.hpc.cineca.it/>

⁴ <https://spack.io/>

- Network for HPC: Mellanox Infiniband 100 Gb/s
- Every compute node is equipped with 2x 24 cores Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 5320 CPU @ 2.20GHz, of which:
 - 1 node with 4x Nvidia A100-80GB and 1024GB of RAM
 - 45 nodes with 512GB of RAM
 - 12 nodes with 1024GB of RAM

Spack Configuration

The Spack instance was installed using a laboratory user account, which will also be used by system administrators for software installation. Within the home directory of the *labswmgr* user, a folder named *SPACK* was created, which will contain the Spack installation (including multiple versions as they become available), the software installed via Spack, and the modulefiles for loading and using the software.

```
mkdir /unimore_home/labswmgr/SPACK
cd /unimore_home/labswmgr/SPACK
git clone -c feature.manyFiles=true --depth=100
--branch=releases/v0.20 https://github.com/spack/spack.git v0.20
```

Spack's modulefile

The Spack instance will be made available through a modulefile, which should contain the following variable settings. Additionally, two other files will need to be sourced: the first, *setup-user-var.sh*, to set certain environment variables useful for managing installations done by regular users; the second, *spack/setup-env.sh*, for Spack initialization.

- Content of the modulefile: the *SPACK_UPSTREAMS_** variables are paths related to the software installed by the *labswmgr* user.

```
set rootdir_name /unimore_home/labswmgr/SPACK
set install_spack_version v0.20
set spack_root_v "$rootdir_name/$install_spack_version"

setenv SPACK_UPSTREAM_INSTALL "$rootdir_name/opt"
setenv SPACK_UPSTREAM_MODULE "$rootdir_name/modulefiles"
setenv SPACK_UPSTREAM_CACHE "$rootdir_name/cache"
prepend-path MODULEPATH
"$rootdir_name/modulefiles/linux-rocky8-icelake"
```

```
source $rootdir_name/module/setup-user-var.sh
source $spack_root_v/share/spack/setup-env.sh
```

- Content of the *setup-user-var.sh* file: the *SPACK_ROOT_** variables are paths related to the software installed by a normal user.

```
# Spack user variables
export SPACK_ROOT_INSTALL=$HOME/SPACK/opt
export SPACK_ROOT_MODULE=$HOME/SPACK/modulefiles
export SPACK_ROOT_CACHE=$HOME/SPACK/cache
export SPACK_ROOT_STAGE=$HOME/SPACK/tmp

# Info for users
echo "Spack activated with "
echo " - upstream install dir: $SPACK_UPSTREAM_INSTALL"
echo " - upstream modules dir: $SPACK_UPSTREAM_MODULE"
echo " - upstream cache dir:   $SPACK_UPSTREAM_CACHE"
echo " - user stage dir:        $SPACK_ROOT_STAGE"
echo ""
echo " $ spack clean --stage      # to clean stage dir"
echo " $ spack clean --downloads  # to clean cache dir"
```

Configuration files:

The environment variables set by the Spack modulefile are used in the Spack configuration files. They are organised hierarchically across four main scopes: *defaults*, *system*, *site*, and *user*. The configuration done is made at the *site* scope level, meaning at the level of the installed Spack instance. This setup allows for different configurations across multiple instances, while also making it easy to transfer configuration files from an older instance to a new one (for example, when upgrading to a new version). The configuration files are in YAML format and, for the *site* scope, should be located in the "*spack_root/etc/spack*" directory. However, they can also be accessed using specific terminal commands. Below, I list the commands to reach the various configuration files, along with some important lines from the files that are relevant to the adopted strategy.

- *config.yaml* to set the user installation paths.

```
spack config --scope site edit config
```

```
config:
```

```
build_stage:
- $SPACK_ROOT_STAGE
source_cache: $SPACK_ROOT_CACHE
install_tree:
  root: $SPACK_ROOT_INSTALL
binary_index_root: $SPACK_ROOT_CACHE
```

- *upstreams.yaml* to set the *labswmgr* installation paths.

spack config --scope site edit upstreams

```
upstreams:
  upstream-production:
    install_tree: $SPACK_UPSTREAM_INSTALL
  modules:
    tcl: $SPACK_UPSTREAM_MODULE
```

- *modules.yaml* to set the variables that have to be defined in the modules and the naming scheme.

spack config --scope site edit modules

```
modules:
  prefix_inspections:
    lib:
      - '{name}_LIB'
      - LD_LIBRARY_PATH
    lib64:
      - '{name}_LIB'
      - LD_LIBRARY_PATH
    include:
      - '{name}_INC'
      - '{name}_INCLUDE'
      - C_INCLUDE_PATH
      - CPATH
    bin:
      - '{name}_BIN'
  default:
    # Where to install modules
    roots:
      tcl: $SPACK_ROOT_MODULE
    # What type of modules to use
    enable:
```

```

    - tcl
  tcl:
    hash_length: 0
    naming_scheme:
' {name}/{version}--{compiler.name}-{compiler.version} '

```

- `packages.yaml` to set the specifications and the path of some external files. This file is particularly interesting because it allows us to define and use the compilers and the mpi wrapper installations provided by the vendor of the cluster.

spack config --scope site edit packages

```

packages:
  gcc:
    externals:
      - spec: gcc@12.1.1
        prefix: /opt/rh/gcc-toolset-12/root/usr
  slurm:
    externals:
      - spec: "slurm@23.02.3 +hwloc +pmix ^hwloc@2.9.1
^pmix@4.2.2"
        prefix: /unimore/prod/sw/gcc-8.5.0/slurm-23.02.3
        buildable: false
  openmpi:
    externals:
      - spec: "openmpi@4.1.5 +cuda cuda_arch=80 +pmi
+singularity fabrics=ucx schedulers=slurm %gcc@12.1.1"
        prefix: /unimore/prod/comps/gcc-12.1.1/ompi-4.1.5_nccl
        buildable: false
        require: cuda@12.0.0%gcc@8.5.0
      - spec: "openmpi@4.1.5 +cuda cuda_arch=80 +pmi
+singularity fabrics=ucx schedulers=slurm %gcc@8.5.0"
        prefix: /unimore/prod/comps/gcc-8.5.0/ompi-4.1.5_nccl
        buildable: false
        require: cuda@12.0.0%gcc@8.5.0

```

- `compilers.yaml` to define all the compilers that can be used by Spack installation instructions.

spack config --scope site edit compilers

How to use Spack on Aries

The following is a brief tutorial on how a user can utilise Spack on Aries, both for accessing software already installed by the system administrators and for installing new software needed by the user. For a more detailed tutorial see the official one on the Spack documentation webpage⁵.

Accessing software installed with Spack

The cluster uses the *Environment Modules*⁶ tool to load and make accessible only the software required by the user. Spack can generate module files compatible with this tool.

To access software installed with Spack by system administrators, you simply need to load the Spack module. This module, in turn, defines several environment variables, including one that enables access to the module files for all software installed via Spack.

```
module load spack
```

Additionally, the same installations can be accessed using Spack's built-in commands. The table below provides a comparison of basic commands, highlighting the equivalent operations between the Modules system and Spack.

Description	Environment Modules	Spack
Listing all the installed software	<code>module avail</code>	<code>spack find</code>
Checking for the availability of a specific software	<code>module avail <i>module_name</i></code>	<code>spack find <i>package_name</i></code>
Loading of the software	<code>module load <i>module_name</i></code>	<code>spack load <i>package_name</i></code>
Listing the loaded software	<code>module list</code>	<code>spack find --loaded</code>
Unloading a software	<code>module unload <i>module_name</i></code>	<code>spack unload <i>package_name</i></code>

⁵ <https://spack-tutorial.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

⁶ <https://modules.readthedocs.io/>

Unloading all the loaded software	<code>module purge</code>	<code>spack unload --all</code>
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Installing software with Spack

The configuration outlined in this report allows users to install software using Spack. This can be useful when a specific software is not provided by system administrators or when a different version (including custom installation specifications) of an available software is needed.

The software will be installed in the user's private area within their home directory. Spack will also handle the creation of the corresponding module files.

The following table lists some useful Spack commands for the installation process.

Description	Spack command
Display a list of all available packages that can be installed using Spack with "world" in their name.	<code>spack list world</code>
Detailed information about a specific package, including configuration options, dependencies, and available versions (<i>specifications</i>).	<code>spack info package_name</code>
List of the compilers available for the installations	<code>spack compilers</code>
Display the full specification of a software package, including its dependency tree and configuration options. Flag "-I" shows if a dependency is already installed.	<code>spack spec -I package_name specifications</code>
Download, build, and install software packages along with their dependencies.	<code>spack install package_name specifications</code>

Basic usage of the command "spack install":

- **Run** "*spack install package_name*" to install a package. For example:

- `spack install hdf5`
downloads and installs HDF5 along with all required dependencies.
- **Variants:** specify build options and features using variants. For example:
 - `spack install hdf5+mpi`
installs HDF5 with MPI support enabled;
 - `spack install hdf5~mpi`
disables MPI support.
- **Version selection:** install a specific version of a package using @. For example:
 - `spack install hdf5@1.12.1`
installs version 1.12.1 of HDF5.
- **Compiler selection:** use % to specify the compiler. For example:
 - `spack install hdf5 %gcc@12.1.1`
installs HDF5 using GCC compiler in version 12.1.1.
- **Customization:** use ^ to specify a dependency. For example:
 - `spack install hdf5 ^mpich`
installs HDF5 with MPICH as the MPI library.

The “`spack spec -I`” command is a powerful tool for previewing how a package will be built, ensuring that the configuration aligns with the user’s needs before installation. Using this command before running “`spack install`” is a good practice to ensure the correct *specifications* for the installation are identified.

Conclusions

At the end of the configuration, I conducted a tutorial for the system administrators of the Aries cluster to explain the specifics of the configuration carried out. Additionally, a brief tutorial on the use of the Spack software was also provided, following the one made available by its developers.

This report summarised the project's development, the setup process with Spack, and the expected benefits for the CNR and university's research community. The first part can be used as a baseline for the setup of new cluster installations, while the second part offers a synthetic user guide both for the installation and the use of the software.

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